

NOTES

Palladium (II) Complexes of Schiff Bases

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In continuation of our work on the transition and non-transition metal complexes of Schiff bases¹⁻⁴, we have isolated some palladium (II) complexes of dibasic quadridentate Schiff bases, bis (salicylidene)-trimethylenediamine (= LH₂) and bis (salicylidene) 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (= L¹H₂). This note describes the spectra of LH₂, L¹H₂, (Pd L), and (PdL¹) in the range 40,000-22,222 cm⁻¹.

Schiff bases were prepared by a previously published method¹. Bis (salicylaldehydato)-palladium (II) was prepared by the method of Sacconi, *et al.*⁵ Palladium (II)-Schiff base complexes were prepared by dissolving bis(salicylaldehydato)-palladium (II) in chloroform and then treating with calculated amount of diamine in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed on water-bath for one hour and filtered. The filtrate, on concentration on water-bath, gave greenish yellow crystals. These were filtered, washed with petroleum ether and dried in vacuum. The complexes are all diamagnetic. Found : Pd, 27.31%; N, 7.81%. Calcd. for (PdL) : Pd, 27.53%; N, 7.24%.

Found : Pd, 26.00%; N, 6.82%, Calcd. for (PdL¹) : Pd, 26.44%; N, 6.96%.

Table-1 shows the spectra of LH₂ and L¹H₂ in ethanol, while the Table-2 records the spectra of [LPd] and [L¹Pd] in nujol mull. The tentative assignments of the bands are also included in the tables. While it is difficult for us to make detailed assignments of the spectral bands of the Pd (II) complexes under investigation at the present moment, the similarity of our spectral results with those of other metallic complexes of dibasic quadridentate Schiff

TABLE 1

Spectra of LH₂ and L¹H₂ in ethanol

LH ₂ ν _{max.} (cm ⁻¹)	L ¹ H ₂ ν _{max.} (cm ⁻¹)	Tentative assignment
39,060	38,910	Aromatic band
35,460	35,460	π → π*
31,750	31,450	π → π*
24,810	24,750	n → π*

TABLE 2

Spectra of (PdL) and (PdL¹) in nujol mull.

(PdL) $\nu_{\max.}$ (cm ⁻¹)	(PdL ¹) $\nu_{\max.}$ (cm ⁻¹)	Tentative assignment
42,870	43,000	
36,870 32,150(Sh)]	36,580 32,083(Sh)]	Aromatic transition region Ligand and charge transfer
25,332 23,090]	25,300 23,000]	

Sh = shoulder.

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bases⁶⁻⁹ and the spectra of the Pd (II) complexes of β -ketoamines¹⁰ allow us to make the present tentative assignments.

Detail work on these systems and similar other systems is in progress and will be communicated in due course.

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REFERENCES

1. K. Dey, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1970, **376**, 209.
2. K. Dey, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3125.
3. K. Dey and K. K. Chatterjee, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1971, **383**, 399.
4. K. Dey, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 887.
5. L. Sacconi, M. Ciampolini, F. Maggio and G. Del Re, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 815.
6. S. M. Crawford, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1963, **19**, 255.
7. B. Bosnich, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 627.
8. R. S. Downing and F. L. Urbach, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 5977.
9. K. S. Patel and J. C. Bailar, Jr., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 1399.
10. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 415.